

THE IMPORTANCE OF FAIRY TALES FOR CHILDREN

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Annotation: *Many believe that fairy tales play an important role in raising their children to be educated, wise, and moral. And that's very true. Fairy tales are better for a child than moral teachings and advice. It inspires confidence in the good, helps to find solutions to difficult situations, builds relationships with people. Fairy tales shape the image of justice, love, friendship, good and evil in a child. This article discusses how fairy tales affect a child's psychology, how they change their behavior, and how fairy tales affect a child's body.*

Keywords: *young generation, spirituality, upbringing, fairy tales, psychology, fairy tale therapy, values*

At present, the education system is becoming more and more determined to rely on the original national values, and the approach to the formation of consciousness, that is, the formation of human spirituality, is becoming a priority. Therefore, if we pay attention to the spiritual upbringing of the younger generation from a young age, it will have a great effect. In order to instill in our children a love and passion for books, we must first treat them properly. There is wisdom in loving literature.

Children are a melodic world living in a world of rapid growth, development and change. This is another proof of the importance of this stage in the upbringing of children. Today, psychologists often point to fairy tale therapy as one of the methods of raising children. Fairy tale therapy is a method of educating and treating a child through fairy tales.

What can fairy tale therapy give to a child?

1. With the help of fairy tale therapy, imagination, creative imagination are developed, peace of mind is achieved.
2. The child learns to analyze the behavior of others and apply this knowledge in their own behavior.
3. Communicative communication is established between the participants through group communication.
4. Fairy tale therapy also helps adults to overcome their phobias and fears, reduce their aggression and anxiety. Through fairy tales, we can

discover and solve problems in a child's heart. Such tales are called therapeutic tales. Often, fairy tales are told before going to bed at night, because the child is calm at this time, which is a good time to influence him. That is why it is necessary to tell positively meaningful tales that end well in the evening. Also, in the family circle, fairy tales listened to by adults provide a basis for problem solving and correction. Fairy tales make a child grow up. First of all, the story should be told to the child with pleasure, so that the child gets more from folk art.

Tales have an active effect on both the mind and the heart: they fill the mind, fill the soul with emotions. We all want our children to grow up to be brave and courageous, religious, faithful and intelligent. To do this, we can use fairy tales that have a positive effect on his upbringing and develop his mental abilities. Reading fairy tales to children has become a tradition in all nations. They help to build a relationship between the child and the parents. Fairy tales are a simplified model of the social world. They teach children to understand society and to overcome difficulties. In addition, the listener is immersed in fairy tale events and alienated from the real world. Maybe that's why in many countries, hospitalized children are read fairy tales. This will help relieve the pain. Researchers have found that fairy tales have a significant positive effect on children's psychological and physical well-being. A study in Brazil found an increase in the interaction hormone oxytocin and a decrease in the stress hormone cortisol when children listened to fairy tales. To determine the effect of fairy tales, scientists studied biomarkers (oxytocin, cortisol), subjective pain sensitivity tests, and psychological impressions. The study involved storytellers and 81 children with extensive experience in the hospital. Pain sensations and saliva samples were examined before and after the interviews with the narrators, as well as perceptions of hospital stay. Studies have shown that an increase in oxytocin and a decrease in cortisol indicate a decrease in pain intensity. There are also significant differences in the analysis of the psycholinguistic situation, for example, before the study of the questions asked: "nurse - an angry aunt who gives bitter medicine", "doctor - a bad man who stabbed me", "hospital - a bad place to leave my home"; The survey was followed by responses such as "nurse is a happy aunt who helps me heal," "doctor is a person who takes care of me," and "hospital is a place where I live until I recover."

Children who are hospitalized experience stress because they suddenly find themselves in an unfamiliar environment, losing contact with parents and friends. At the same time, reading fairy tales helps to reduce the

subjective feeling of pain and relieve stress in children who are alone in the hospital. In addition, this method is also the most convenient for every parent.

Due to the problem of fairy tales, fairy tale therapy should be removed in a timely manner.

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